

ISic4375

Fragmentary Latin inscription

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance

Found during rescue excavations in 2015, in the area immediately to the north of the Cimitero Comunale, in surface layers above Roman period tombs within a late-antique basilica

Coordinates

37.990150, 13.689428

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Termini Imerese

Physical Description

Upper left corner of a marble plaque

Dimensions

Height 7 cm

Width 10 cm

Depth 2 cm

Layout

Beginning of two lines of Latin letters preserved

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Large, formally v-cut letters with minimal serifs

Letter heights:

Line 1: not recorded mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: not recorded mm

Text

1. M · A[---]

2. C · f[---]

Apparatus

CE (?), Chiovaro and Rondinella

Translation**Commentary****Digital identifiers:**

Bibliography

Chiovaro, Monica, Rondinella, Maria Teresa 2017. Nuove scoperte nelle necropoli di Termini Imerese. *Notiziario Archeologico della Soprintendenza di Palermo*. 22: 1-31. At 27 fig.76

Licensed under a Creative Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-21): ISic4375. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4381832>